

CHARACTERISTICS OF EXHIBITING EMOTIONAL STATUS IN RELATION TO EDUCATION IN ADOLESCENT PERIOD

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The ability to worry about various things is characteristic of a person, which indicates that he is not indifferent to life. However, this anxiety is sometimes in an inadequate form, that is, a person experiences this condition without justification. The diversity of the concept of anxiety as a mental state comes from the fact that different researchers interpret the concept of "Anxiety" in different ways.

Anxiety is a tendency of a person to constantly feel anxious, to perceive various situations as dangerous. The experience of anxiety is also an individual characteristic, and such a feeling appears before an uncertain danger. Anxiety causes changes in habits and situations that may or may not occur. It is manifested in anxious actions, tension of the situation, etc. A high level of anxiety usually reduces the effectiveness of the activity, it is accompanied by various conflicting behavior of the person. Generally, two types of situational anxiety are distinguished as a personality trait. Trait anxiety is an anxiety state characterized by nervous system characteristics and prolonged unpleasant communication anxiety or reactive anxiety that is associated with a specific situation and does not manifest itself outside of it [1].

The anxiety scale developed by A.M.Prikhajan is based on the principle of Kondash's "Social situational" anxiety scale, which identifies the main sources and level of anxiety [2].

The methodology is used by practical psychologists for the purpose of psychoprophylaxis of the "concern" group of students, i.e. students and their parents who probably do not even turn to a psychologist, but there are no opportunities, but behind external acceptability, certain personal conflicts are hidden, as a result of defects in the development of self-esteem, subjective feeling of small failures in serious areas of activity and communication. can be used to identify students.

In order to study the level of anxiety in a person, the method of determining personal anxiety was carried out in a group of testers, and the results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality. The results of quantitative analysis are presented in tables and diagrams.

Table 1

Results on the method of determining personal anxiety

Testers	Types of anxiety		
	Anxiety about school	Anxiety about self-esteem	Anxiety about interpersonal relationships
8th grade	20%	42%	38%
9th grade	16%	45%	39%

If we pay attention to the results of the table, it became clear that the test subjects have a high index of each type of anxiety in the personality of a small teenager. According to the analysis of the results, anxiety about school is 20% among 8th graders and 16% among 9th graders.

From this it can be concluded that small teenage students are not fully adapted to an educational institution, do not perceive the social environment Tula, do not realize the essence of the role and functions of a student, the requirements imposed by an educational institution weigh on them, and also adapt to a new environment can be characterized by finding a person close to him. Also, the situation in the educational institution, the difficulty in communicating with teachers and the attitude of teachers towards students are determined by the presence of anxiety in them.

Anxiety related to self-assessment is 42% among 8th graders and 45% among 9th graders. From the analysis of the results, it can be seen that it is much higher in junior high school students, which can be explained by the fact that they do not fully understand their possibilities and abilities and cannot demonstrate them in their practical activities. Older teenage students have a much lower level, and they fully demonstrate their potential and abilities. Also, the fact that they have adequate self-evaluation skills leads to a decrease in their anxiety. It is known that if we focus on the self-evaluation system during this period, we can see that they have a somewhat adequate appearance. At the same time, we can see that it is important for them to react with the understanding of their capabilities and abilities, rather than the evaluation given by others. Communication is a form of interpersonal relations with the help of which people enter into a psychological relationship with each other, exchange information, influence, be affected, perceive, understand and evaluate processes. Therefore, treatment is a social psychological phenomenon, a social category that directly participates in all spheres of social life, arises as an objective and

subjective need that reflects the material, spiritual, emotional, cognitive, motivational, and regulatory aspects of cooperative activity, and acts as the main factor and basis of socialization.

Among the test subjects, 38% of students of the 8th grade were worried about interpersonal relationships. This is explained by the fact that they have not fully penetrated into the life of society, the lack of sincere communication between group members, dissatisfaction with joint activities, and the existence of a normal social and psychological environment in the group. In the case of 9th grade students, this indicator is 39%, which indicates that they have formed the skills of interaction and communication between group members. We can see from the results that the anxiety in interpersonal relations is often explained by the lack of formation of personal characteristics and communication skills.

The results of the methodology show that a higher level of anxiety in a person indicates a higher level of self-esteem, and a higher level of self-esteem indicates a lower level of anxiety. Also, in many cases, anxiety determined the position, position, status and communication skills of the person in the team. It should be mentioned that the development of a person is not a smooth process, therefore, changes occur due to various external influences, people around them, characteristics of the age period. Of course, it is important to consider these aspects in the formation of personality.

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